

Dazhidu lun 大智度論

also known as “Commentary on the Great Perfection of Wisdom”,
“Mahāprajñāpāramitopadeśa”, “Mahāprajñāpāramitā Upadeśa”

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Indic Religious Traditions, Chinese Religion, Scripture, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist text, Text, Religious Group, Mādhyamika school (sanlun zong 三論宗), Scholastic traditions of Mahāyāna in India, Mahayana Buddhism, Indic Buddhist Traditions

The Commentary on the Great Perfection of Wisdom (Sanskrit: Mahāprajñāpāramitā Upadeśa; Chinese: Dàzhìdù Lùn) is a bright jewel in the treasury of the world’s religious and philosophical literature. Its monumental size, vast scope and rich content have already sealed its place in humanities spiritual legacy. Composed by one of the most remarkable yet enigmatic figures of Buddhism, the legendary Nāgārjuna, this commentary on the Great Perfection of Wisdom Scripture builds on the ancient traditions of early Buddhism, adds scholastic systematic analysis, and rallies together the scriptures and treatises of Mahāyāna Buddhism, to champion the Madhyamaka “Middle Way” of the Bodhisattva’s spiritual path to the omniscience of a fully awakened Buddha. It took the master translator Kumārajīva and his team of elite Chinese Buddhist scholars to do justice to such a work of genius, producing a translation that matched Nāgārjuna’s religious and philosophical content with a standard of literary excellence, which itself brought about a new zenith in classical Chinese Buddhist writing. This translation, which is now our only source of the original text, was a veritable gold mine of Indian Buddhist legend and lore, thought and ideas, practice and theory, for subsequent generations of Chinese Buddhists. As first a central column for the Three Treatise and Tiantai schools, it functioned as an important point of reference for the Pure Land and Chan schools, and also the Flower Adornment and Discipline schools, thus permeating the entirety of classical Chinese Buddhism. In modern China and Taiwan, its status has not only continued, but been further enhanced, by the call of Humanistic Buddhism which highly values the human centered focus of this ancient Indian Buddhist text.

Date Range: 402 CE - 406 CE

Region: General range of use for the Dazhidu lun

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, Japan, Vietnam, East Asia, South Korea, North Korea

From Latter Qin dynasty China, expanding through East Asia to include present day China, Korea, Japan and Vietnam.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Lamotte, Étienne. *Le Traite de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse, de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitā śāstra)*. Tome II. Chapitres XV-XXX. Université de Louvain: Institut Orientaliste Louvain-la-Neuve, 1981

[1949].

- Source 2: Lamotte, Étienne. Le Traite de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse, de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitā śāstra). Tome III. Chapitres XXXI-XLII. Université de Louvain: Institut Orientaliste Louvain-la-Neuve, 1970.
- Source 3: Lamotte, Étienne. Le Traite de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse, de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitā śāstra). Tome IV. Chapitres XLII (suite)-XLVIII. Université de Louvain: Institut Orientaliste Louvain-la-Neuve, 1976.
- Source 1: Lamotte, Étienne. Le Traite de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse, de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitā śāstra). Tome V. Chapitres XLIX-LII, et Chapitre XX (2e série). Université de Louvain: Institut Orientaliste Louvain-la-Neuve, 1980.
- Source 1: Editorial Committee of the Japanese Tripiṭaka, Takakusu Junjirō ed., Taishō Shinshū Daizokyo, vol. 25, pp. 57-756. 1924-1932.
- Source 2: Lamotte, Étienne. Le Traite de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse, de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitā śāstra). Tome I. Chapitres I-XV. Université de Louvain: Institut Orientaliste Louvain-la-Neuve, 1981 [1944].

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy01.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. I
- Source 2 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy02.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. II
- Source 3 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy03.pdf
- Source 3 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. III
- Source 1 URL: <http://www.buddhism-dict.net/cgi-bin/xpr-ddb.pl?q=%E5%A4%A7%E6%99%BA%E5%BA%A6%E8%AB%96>
- Source 1 Description: Digital Dictionary of Buddhism entry (requires login, username 'guest', no password)
- Source 1 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy04.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. IV
- Source 2 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy05.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. V
- Source 3 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy06.pdf
- Source 3 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. VI
- Source 1 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy04.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. IV
- Source 2 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy05.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. V

- Source 3 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy06.pdf
- Source 3 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. VI
- Source 1 URL: https://www.yinshun.org.tw/download/freebook/C_dzdljy07.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Edited edition with annotation of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, vol. VII
- Source 1 URL: <https://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T25n1509>
- Source 1 Description: Edited edition of the Chinese text of the Dazhidu lun, based on the Taisho edition

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T25n1509>
- Source 1 Description: CBETA online edition of Dazhidu lun

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

- ↳ Method of inscription
 - Chisel

- Written

- ↳ Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: Not sure

- Stone

- Wood

|

- ↳ Species
 - Specify: Not sure

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: None

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

- Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

- Yes

- ↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?
 - No

- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
 - No

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- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - No

- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - No

- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - No

- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - I don't know

- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present full-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 2000000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 2000000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 1

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 1000000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Growing populations, medium used

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 5

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 1

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 5

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Growing populations, medium used

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Yes

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience differ?

– Specify: Emic assessments would include all sentient beings, esp. humans and gods

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience be similar?

– Specify: In terms of the humans involved, especially intellectual types

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Notes: The question of whether the text is Indic or Chinese in origin

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

– Specify: By the general type of Buddhist literature, e.g. Sutra, Vinaya and Sastra; then in turn through various types of each

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: It is scripture

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Commentary on sutra

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: Abhidharma system of various material and mental phenomena (dharmas), beyond a simple spirit-body relationship

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: The aggregates are the basis of dukkha (dissatisfaction)

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Positivity or negativity depends on ethical states of mind, not all states in general

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The Pudgalavadins/Vatsiputriyas argued for a 'pudgala' (individual) that was neither identical with nor different from the aggregates.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

–Specify: Position one: there are five realms of rebirth; Position two: there are six realms of rebirth

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Neither is particularly minority, both are fairly common and there is not that intense debate about the matter.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession?
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: None
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: An entire range of different personality types, motivations, intentions, abilities

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The world is divided into three realms, the desire, form and formless. The former are more coarse material forms with attendant sufferings, the latter are increasingly non-material, but still suffer.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Devas/gods, asuras/titas, humans, animals, ghosts/spirits, hell beings

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

- No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: 1. Killing of living beings. 2. Testing those who claim to be irreversible bodhisattvas.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– No

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Granting boons / wishes.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– No

↳ Coming on a specified date

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: A religious figure who will start the next round of teachings (which are eternal truths).

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only specialized religious class

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Meditation / concentration / mental absorption

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

- ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - No
- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - No
- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Flowers, incense, banners, flags, precious treasures
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Elite Buddhist scholar

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Encourages kings, etc. to engage in this

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: Encourages kings, etc. to engage in this

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Encourages kings, etc. to engage in welfare in general

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– I don't know

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chapters of the text refer to specific teacher-student relationships.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?
– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?
– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood

control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: None

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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